

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Push and Pull Travel Motivations of Tourists Engaged in DIY Travel

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Abstract

This research explored the push and pull travel motivations influencing tourists who engage in do-it-yourself (DIY) travel. It aimed to know how internal desires and characteristics of attractions influenced the travel decision and overall experience of the respondents. Employing a descriptive-correlational design, the study collected responses from foreign tourists who visited destinations across the Philippines. Findings showed that the “push” motivations included the desire to escape from daily routines, seek adventure and challenge, gain self-development, and satisfy curiosity through new discoveries. On the other hand, external or “pull” motivations such as attractive destinations, safety and security, accessibility, and affordability significantly encouraged travelers to choose specific places. This study concluded the significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the level of their push and pull motivations, the findings allow the researcher to provide a comprehensive travel plan strategy.

Keywords: DIY Travel; Push and Pull Travel Motivation; Tourist Behavior; Travel Experiences

1 Introduction

Tourism is a multi-branched global industry driven by a huge number of factors like economic forces and by the varied motivations of people looking for valuable experiences with their travels. Understanding these motivations is central to both tourism development and the effective engagement of travelers. One of the most widely known models in this field is the Push and Pull Motivation Framework, originally conceptualized by Dann (1977) and further developed by Crompton (1979). This dual-dimensional theory divides the idea between push factors, which are internal, psychological forces that initiate the desire to travel, and pull factors, which are the external characteristics of a destination that attract visitors.

In the context of the Philippine tourism, it continues to produce economic and cultural force, and there has been an eminent rise in DIY (Do-It-Yourself) travel where it is a self-directed, thus tourism slowly favored by foreign visitors as cited in the journal of Fernandez, et al., (2019). Do-It Yourself or most commonly called (DIY) travel has allowed individuals to self-organize and customize their travel according to their preferred approaches. This is made possible with the help of technology, specifically the online booking platform. The trend of DIY travel is especially really well known to those groups of individuals who are budget conscious, and tourists who are seeking a more flexible and customized tour. DIY travel is really a game changer specifically when it comes to affordability and authentic experience tourists may experience.

The push and pull motivation factors are one of the theories that are widely accepted in Tourism and Hospitality. This is a model used to analyze the internal and external drives. In today's era, the increasing popularity of DIY is on the rise, particularly among foreign tourists visiting the Philippines. With the help of digital platforms, global mobility, and the shift toward self-organized travel, DIY tourism has become the preferred option for tourists seeking a flexible, affordable, and culturally immersive experience. We are very aware that the Philippines has diverse attractions, as it is

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rich in culture and tradition, and offers relatively low-cost travel to its tourist destinations. However, according to limited research, such as the 2024 article entitled "Exploring push and pull factors in tourism: Understanding foreign visitors' motivation in Siquijor Island", this research article explores and addresses how the push and pull motivation factors influence the decision of foreign visitors who are engaged in DIY travel in visiting the Philippines. In this sense, there is a need to investigate how the profiles of travelers, such as age, sex/gender, educational attainment, income, travel companions, and preferred booking methods, intersect with the push and pull motivations that shape and influence tourist preferences and behavior. By examining and analyzing the push and pull factors influencing DIY travel, as well as its relationship to travelers' demographics, this study will address the gaps in tourism practices and the existing literature. The findings will then be applied to the strategic management of stakeholders, as well as to business owners in the Hospitality and Tourism Industry. The results and findings can contribute to the inclusive and more sustainable tourism experience and practice.

2 Material and Methods

This study utilized a descriptive correlational design where the researcher seeks to identify the characteristics of certain groups of people or find relationships between different variables (Author, 2024). This design was anchored in this study to explore and understand the push and pull motivations and experiences of travelers who engage in DIY budget-friendly tours. Moreover, it allows the researcher to describe the participants' demographic profiles and perceptions, while examining potential relationships between variables— travel frequency, involvement, satisfaction, and engagement. Descriptive correlational design validated the findings of the data where structured data analysis yielded reliability of the data. By incorporating methods, this can further investigate and examine the dynamic impact of push and pull motivations in engaging in budget-friendly travels in local destinations. The researcher applied a non-probability sampling method in choosing respondents, making sure that only respondents who matched the criteria of this study would provide their insights and responses. This method enables the researcher to carefully examine and verify the raw collected data to maintain accuracy and consistency of results, and to provide comprehensive findings. The researcher ensured that a systematic process was applied to accomplish this study to provide a well-supported and evidence-based results discussion and comprehensive conclusion.

3 Results and Discussion

Part 1 Socio-demographic profile of the respondents

The following table is the results pertaining the Socio-demographic profile of the respondents including the age, sex, nationality, civil status, educational attainment, employment status, monthly income, length of stay in the Philippines, number of places visited in the Philippines, purpose of visit, travel companions, and preferred booking method.

Table 1 Socio-demographic profile of the respondents

Category	Details / Findings	Key Insight
Age	Majority were 25–35 years old	Most active age group of travelers
Sex	Male: 56%Female: 44%	Men were the predominant travelers
Nationality	Americans: 19%Canadians: 18%Other nationalities: remaining percentage	Americans formed the largest group
Civil Status	Married: 63%	Married individuals were the most active travelers
Employment Status	Employed: 72%	Stable employment increases travel capacity
Monthly Income	78% earned \$885 or more	Higher income enhances financial ability to travel
Length of Stay in the Philippines	3–4 weeks: 41%	Respondents preferred immersive travel experiences
Number of Destinations Visited	Five destinations: 40%	High interest in exploring Philippine attractions

Purpose of Travel	Adventure and challenge: 32%	Outdoor and nature-based activities are primary motivations
Preferred Booking Method	Booking applications: 50%	Strong reliance on technology for real-time transactions

3.1 Part 2 Push Travel Motivations

The following tables represent and interpret the data collected addressing the top push travel motivations of foreign tourists. This portion examines and verifies the statements of the perceived push motivation of foreign tourists. The interpretation emphasizes the key findings relevant to achieve the objectives of the study.

Table 2 Percentage and Frequency of Escape from Routine

No.	Escape From Routine	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1	Escaping my repetitive schedule is a key reason I choose to travel.	3.22	0.77	Agree
2	Travel allows me to mentally refresh by stepping away from my usual environment.	3.28	0.64	Strongly Agree
3	I prioritize travel to gain new perspectives that my daily life cannot provide.	3.29	0.71	Strongly Agree
4	The desire to avoid burnout from my routine pushes me to plan trips.	3.32	0.69	Strongly Agree
5	Exploring unfamiliar cultures or places helps me feel liberated from my routine.	3.25	0.70	Strongly Agree
6	Experiencing new environments helps me temporarily forget my daily responsibilities.	3.28	0.68	Strongly Agree
7	Traveling helps me disconnect from my social or professional obligations	3.24	0.71	Agree
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.27	0.47	Strongly Agree

The survey finds that the statement "The desire to avoid burnout from my routine pushes me to plan trips" got the highest mean score of 3.32. This means that respondents considered it as a significant reason to travel. Moreover, tourists want to travel to avoid the feeling of stress and worn out from their everyday life. On the other hand, the statement "Escaping my repetitive schedule is a key reason I choose to travel" got the lowest mean score of 3.22, even if it is a bit lower, it still shows that people agree with this idea.

Table 3 Percentage and frequency of Adventure and Challenge

No.	Adventure And Challenge	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1	Challenging myself physically is a key reason I choose adventurous destinations.	3.22	0.70	Agree
2	Overcoming fears during travel motivates me to explore new places.	3.34	0.67	Strongly Agree
3	Trips that have unpredictable/ risky experiences motivate me to visit the destination.	3.23	0.84	Agree
4	Traveling allows me to test my mental resilience in unfamiliar situations.	3.34	0.74	Strongly Agree
5	Destinations known for extreme or unconventional adventures pushes me to travel.	3.30	0.75	Strongly Agree
6	The thrill of exploring untamed natural environments drives my travel decisions.	3.27	0.72	Strongly Agree

7	A travel experience that allows travelers to conquer personal limitations is my drive to travel.	3.27	0.75	Strongly Agree
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.28	0.57	Strongly Agree

The results show that the statements "Overcoming fears during travel motivates me to explore new places" and "Traveling allows me to test my mental resilience in unfamiliar situations" both had the highest average score of 3.34. This means that self-discovery and resilience are top reasons why they travel. On the other hand, the statement "Challenging myself physically is a key reason I choose adventurous destinations" got the lowest mean of 3.22, but still considered and interpreted as agree.

Table 4 Percentage and Frequency of Self-Development and Learning

No.	Self-Development And Learning	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1	Learning about different cultures motivates me to plan trips.	3.47	0.56	Strongly Agree
2	Traveling allows me to develop skills I cannot acquire in my daily life.	3.45	0.61	Strongly Agree
3	A country renowned for its high-quality education serves as a significant motivation to me to pursue studies abroad and remain there until graduation.	3.37	0.69	Strongly Agree
4	Immersing myself in unfamiliar environments helps me understand myself better.	3.31	0.76	Strongly Agree
5	Destinations offering educational experiences in history, art, and science serve as my primary motivators for visitation.	3.36	0.66	Strongly Agree
6	Engaging with local communities motivates me to learn about their traditions and motivates me to travel more.	3.36	0.70	Strongly Agree
7	Learning a new language or skill during travel is my key motivation.	3.40	0.70	Strongly Agree
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.39	0.49	Strongly Agree

Based on the table above, the statement "Learning about different cultures motivates me to plan trips" got the highest mean score of 3.4, this means that cultural immersion is one of the priorities of the foreign tourist. This suggests that the tourist has a desire to expand their knowledge and experience about the culture of different countries. On the other hand, "Immersing myself in an unfamiliar environment helps me understand myself better" got the lowest mean score of 3.31. While it got the lowest score, but still it considered as "Strongly Agree"

Table 5 Percentage and Frequency of Novelty and Exploration

No.	Novelty And Exploration	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1	Exploring unfamiliar places is a primary reason I choose to travel.	3.35	0.67	Strongly Agree
2	Discovering hidden gems motivates me to explore new regions.	3.20	0.71	Agree
3	Traveling allows me to satisfy my curiosity about the world.	3.35	0.76	Strongly Agree
4	Experiencing different lifestyles inspires me to plan trips.	3.32	0.72	Strongly Agree
5	Destination that has indigenous cultures motivates me to travel and visit the place to experience firsthand the beauty of their tradition	3.30	0.72	Strongly Agree
6	Visiting remote or isolated locations is a key motivation for me.	3.26	0.73	Strongly Agree
7	The need to experience something new and different pushes me to travel.	3.34	0.71	Strongly Agree
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.30	0.55	Strongly Agree

Based on the table above, the statement *"Exploring unfamiliar places is a primary reason I choose to travel"* and *"Travelling allows me to satisfy my curiosity about the world"* both got the highest mean score of 3.35. This means that seeking a new experience and exploring unfamiliar or not famous tourist destinations can be considered as a motivation to travel as it can satisfy the curiosity of the travelers. On the other hand, the statement *"Discovering hidden gems motivates me to explore new regions"* got the lowest mean score of 3.20, but respondents also agreed with it.

3.2 Part 3: Pull Travel Motivations

The following table presents collected data that interpret the findings for the top pull travel motivations of the foreign tourists. This portion aimed to provide an insight that addresses the objectives of the study and to enhance the understanding of the factors influencing the pull motivations of the study.

Table 6 Percentage and Frequency of Tourism Infrastructure and Services

No.	Tourism Infrastructure and Services	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1	The destination's airport/ports were modern and well maintained	3.28	0.68	Strongly Agree
2	Public transportation was efficient and easy to use.	3.25	0.67	Strongly Agree
3	Road conditions and signage made it easy to navigate the destination.	3.34	0.68	Strongly Agree
4	The availability of diverse accommodation (e.g., hotel, motels, and homestays) influenced my decision to visit.	3.45	0.64	Strongly Agree
5	Clean and well-maintained public restrooms in the frequently visited local tourist destinations were readily available.	3.37	0.69	Strongly Agree
6	Tourist information centers provided helpful guidance and resources.	3.46	0.61	Strongly Agree
7	Availability of multi-lingual services (e.g., tour guides, signage) enhanced my travel experience.	3.40	0.64	Strongly Agree
8	Local staff (e.g., hotel, restaurant) were friendly and professional.	3.48	0.59	Strongly Agree
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.86	0.55	Strongly Agree

According to the results, the statement "Local staff (e.g., hotel, restaurant) were friendly and professional" got the highest mean score of .48, this means that foreign tourists love and appreciate being treated professionally, as they highly value hospitality and professionalism. This also highlights the importance of being kind as positive interaction can really improve the tourist's satisfaction. On the other hand, the statement "Public transportation was efficient and easy to use" got the lowest mean score of 3.25. While this is still considered as strongly agreed, it suggests that there is a room for public transportation improvement to better serve the tourist.

Table 7 Percentage and Frequency of Cost and Affordability

No.	Cost And Affordability	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1	The overall value-for-money of the specific local tourist destination motivated me to travel.	3.47	0.56	Strongly Agree
2	The availability of budget-friendly dining/ fast-food options was a key factor in selecting a tourist destination.	3.39	0.58	Strongly Agree
3	Transparent pricing (e.g., no hidden fees for attractions/activities) increased my interest in visiting.	3.48	0.63	Strongly Agree
4	Discount, promotions, or seasonal deals, played a role in my decision to travel.	3.54	0.61	Strongly Agree
5	The perceived affordability of local transportation (e.g., buses, taxis) encouraged me to visit.	3.47	0.64	Strongly Agree

6	The general affordability of shopping/souvenirs influenced my choice to visit a specific destination.	3.45	0.61	Strongly Agree
7	Having a diverse choice of accommodations (from cheap-expensive) to a tourist destination is more appealing to me.	3.48	0.59	Strongly Agree
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.47	0.45	Strongly Agree

Based on the table above, the statement "Discount, promotion, or seasonal deals played a role in my decision to travel" got the highest mean score of 3.54. These findings mean that the decision-making of travelers has a strong connection with the promotional offers and discounts in choosing the place to go. On the other hand, the statement "The availability of budget-friendly dining/fast-food options was a key factor in selecting a tourist destination" got the lowest mean score of 3.39. While it is considered "Strongly Agree", it means that affordable dining is necessary, but not that influential to travelers who are seeking to try different cuisines.

Table 8 Percentage and Frequency of Attraction and Activities

No.	Attraction And Activities	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1	Visiting historical sites (e.g. museums, monuments) was the key reason for me to travel.	3.36	0.66	Strongly Agree
2	The reputation of the destination's heritage and cultural attractions influenced my decision to visit	3.38	0.66	Strongly Agree
3	The scenic beauty of specific destinations (e.g., beaches, mountains) strongly attracted me.	3.49	0.64	Strongly Agree
4	Opportunities to explore natural landmarks (e.g., parks, wildlife) influence my travel choice.	3.50	0.67	Strongly Agree
5	The availability of outdoor and adventurous activities (e.g., hiking, water sports) motivated me to visit.	3.44	0.66	Strongly Agree
6	The variety of leisure activities (e.g., spas, shopping, and gym) impacted my decision to travel.	3.33	0.71	Strongly Agree
7	The presence of cultural and native activities (eg, cultural shows, festivals) in a destination made it more appealing to me to visit the place.	3.39	0.68	Strongly Agree
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.41	0.54	Strongly Agree

Based on the table above, the statement "Opportunities to explore natural landmarks (e.g., parks, wildlife)" got the highest mean score of 3.50. This means that tourists are interested in places where they can explore nature and engage in outdoor activities. Travelers see natural landmarks as an important characteristic that makes a tourist destination more appealing. On the other hand, the statement "The variety of leisure activities (e.g., spas, shopping, and gym) impacted my decision to travel" got the lowest mean score of 3.33.

Table 9 Percentage and Frequency of Safety and Security

No.	Safety And Security	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1	Safe and secure accommodations significantly influence my choice of travel destinations.	3.43	0.64	Strongly Agree
2	Reliable public transportation safety (e.g., low crime rates on buses/trains) is important to me when planning travel.	3.42	0.59	Strongly Agree
3	The availability of reliable emergency services (e.g., hospitals, tourist helplines) impacts my choice of destination.	3.45	0.64	Strongly Agree
4	Safe infrastructure (e.g., well-lit streets, pedestrian safety) is critical to my travel preferences.	3.45	0.63	Strongly Agree
5	A local community's friendliness and tolerance toward tourists affect my decision to visit.	3.45	0.64	Strongly Agree
6	Safe nightlife options (e.g., secure bars, clubs, and entertainment zones) are important in my travel decisions.	3.36	0.69	Strongly Agree
7	Visible security measures (e.g., police presence, surveillance cameras) make a destination more appealing to me.	3.40	0.68	Strongly Agree
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.42	0.50	Strongly Agree

The table shown above shows the statement "The availability of reliable emergency services (e.g., hospitals, tourist helplines) impact my choice of destination," "Safe infrastructure (e.g., well-lit streets, pedestrian safety) is critical to my travel preferences," and "A local community's friendliness and tolerance toward tourists affect my decision to visit" got the highest mean score of 3.45. This means that a destination with accessible emergency services, safe and secure public spaces, and most importantly, a friendly community.

Part 4: Significant relationship between the profile of foreign tourist and their level of push motivation

Results revealed several significant associations. A positive correlation indicates that as one variable increases, the other variable also increases. In this study, a positive correlation means that when a respondent's profile characteristic (such as nationality, civil status, or income) increases or differs in a certain way, their level of push motivations such as the desire for escape, adventure, or self-development also tends to increase.

On the other hand, a negative correlation means that as one variable increases, the other decreases. In this context, a negative correlation suggests that certain profile characteristics are inversely related to specific travel motivations.

Nationality correlated positively with Novelty and Exploration ($r = .200$) This implies that Thai respondents tended to have a better push motivation as to novelty and exploration. Civil status showed a positive and significant correlation with Escape from Routine ($r = .264$) and Self-development and Learning ($r = .209$), this means that female respondents tended to have better motivation to escape from routine and self-development and learning. In other factors, estimated monthly income displayed a positive and significant correlation with Adventure and Challenge ($r = .216$). This implies that individuals with higher income levels may have greater capacity and willingness to engage in adventurous activities or destinations that require more financial resources.

On the other hand, Purpose of visit exhibited negative correlations with Escape from Routine ($r = -.357$) and Adventure and Challenge ($r = -.314$). This means that those respondents' purpose is leisure and recreation tended to increase the motivation to escape from an adventure and challenge. Furthermore, Travel companion was found to have negative correlations with Escape from Routine ($r = -.254$), self-development ($r = -.230$), and novelty ($r = -.296$). Solo travelers tended to have better motivation as to escape from routine, self-development and learning and novelty exploration, which may also suggest that traveling with others can lessen one's drive for personal exploration or novelty-seeking experiences. Similarly, Preferred Booking method showed negative correlations with Adventure and challenge ($r = -.368$) and Novelty and exploration ($r = -.210$), indicating that direct booking tended the respondents to have push motivation as to adventure and challenge and novelty exploration

Given these significant relationships, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between respondents' demographic profile and their psychological travel motivations is rejected.

Part 5: Significant relationship between the profile of foreign tourist and their level of pull motivation

The findings revealed that educational attainment has a significant positive correlation with Safety and security ($r = 0.247$), suggesting that higher educational levels (Post graduate degree holder) are associated with greater concern for travel safety and security measures. Similarly, Employment status showed a significant negative correlation with Tourism infrastructure and services ($r = -0.221$) and Safety and security ($r = -0.236$) implying that employed respondents tended to have better pull motivation in terms of tourism infrastructure and service and safety and security. Purpose of visit also exhibited a significant negative relationship with Tourism infrastructure and services ($r = -0.198$), this means that those respondents whose purpose is for leisure and recreation tended to increase their pull motivation as to tourism infrastructure and services. While, Travel companions exhibited a negative correlation with Attraction and activities ($r = -0.214$) implying that solo travelers tended to increase pull motivation as to attraction and activities.

Preferred booking method ($r = -0.296$) were negatively correlated with Attractions and activities, indicating that social and logistical factors play a role in shaping travel perceptions. Although estimated monthly income showed a positive but insignificant relationship across all variables, the direction suggests that higher income may enhance satisfaction with destination factors.

Based on these results, it can be inferred that selected demographic and travel-related variables significantly influence perceptions of destination quality. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating no significant relationship between respondents' profile and their perceptions of destination factors is rejected. These findings are supported by Rahman, Gani, and Rahman (2020), who found that socio-demographic characteristics such as education, income, and occupation significantly affect tourists' satisfaction and destination evaluation patterns.

Part 6: Proposed DIY Travel Plan Strategy for Foreign Tourists Visiting the Philippines

Based on the findings, a Personalized Experience-Based DIY Travel Plan Strategy is proposed to enhance the motivational satisfaction of foreign tourists visiting the Philippines. The correlation analysis showed that demographic and situational factors such as nationality, civil status, income, purpose of visit, travel companion, and booking method significantly affect tourists' internal (push) motivations. Thus, based on the overall findings of the statement number 5, a DIY (Do-It-Yourself) Travel Plan Strategy is proposed to enhance the travel experience of foreign tourists visiting the Philippines. The results revealed that respondents strongly agreed across all factors such as tourism infrastructure and services, cost and affordability, attractions and activities, and safety and security, indicating that these elements significantly shape their travel (pull) motivations and satisfaction.

Below is the proposed travel strategy for the tourists that are engaged in DIY travel.

- Cultural Immersion and Novelty Exploration- Since nationality correlated positively with novelty and exploration, the plan suggests promoting unique Filipino cultural and heritage experiences (e.g., local festivals, traditional cuisine tours, and community-based tourism).
- Rest and Rejuvenation Packages: Civil status is closely linked to the desire for escape and self-development. Travelers are seeking personal growth and relaxation; most of the time, they consider visiting a serene tourist destination, such as pristine white beaches, retreats, wellness spas, and nature activities.
- Adventurous Itinerary for High-Income Tourists. Since higher income is associated with a greater interest in adventure activities, the plan should offer a premium package that includes activities such as scuba diving in Palawan, surfing in Siargao Island, trekking in Banaue rice terraces, and many more for travelers seeking adventure and challenge.
- Solo Traveler Itineraries. The finding reveals that solo travelers are primarily motivated by the desire to escape, self-development, and novelty and exploration. It suggests that itineraries with guided yet independent tours can help them discover themselves and explore authentically.
- Safety- Centered Travel Design- Findings revealed that safety and security obtained the overall weighted mean. The DIY travel plan should start with finding safe accommodation, well-lit streets, and accessible emergency services in the destination.
- Smart Infrastructure and Service Utilization- Findings revealed that infrastructure and services have a significant impact on the tourists' choices. The travel plan strategy encourages the use of online transportation

applications, online booking applications, and other online tools to help tourists plan flexible travel without relying on a travel agency.

- **Cost-Efficient Itinerary Building.** Findings revealed that cost and affordability are important to many travelers. The travel plan suggests and recommends budget-friendly options such as guesthouses, low-cost flights to the destination, and public transportation. This will help tourists manage their spending and maximize the value of their trips.
- **Experience-Based Attraction Planning.** Findings revealed that attraction and activities are important to travelers, the travel plan strategy recommends incorporating cultural, historical, and natural sites into their travel itineraries.

4 Conclusion

4.1 The following are the conclusions covering the demographic profile of the respondents

The findings revealed that most of the respondents were 25 to 35 years old, and they are the most active travelers in groups. The findings also revealed that most of the respondents are male (56%), while females are 44%. This indicates that men are predominantly the active travelers in this study. Americans made up the largest group of respondents with a total of 19%, followed by Canadians with a total of 18%. The rest of the respondents were from other nationalities. In terms of civil status, most of the respondents were married, and had a total of 63%, which means that married individuals were the most active travelers within this group. In terms of employment status, a huge portion of the respondents were employed (72%), indicating that a stable income enhances their capacity and motivation to travel. Employment status plays a key role in influencing travel engagement. In relation to this aspect, a huge portion of the respondents (78%) earned \$885 or more per month, which means that they have the financial capacity to travel. It is also true that the income level is a key factor in travel engagement. In terms of the level of their stays in the Philippines, most of the respondents (41%) stayed in the Philippines for three to four weeks. This suggests that tourists preferred a more immersive travel experience.

When it comes to the number of visited destinations, most of the respondents (40%) visited five destinations, which means that this reflects their strong interest in the Philippines' tourist destination; this also means a high level of motivation. In terms of the purpose of travel, most of the respondents visited the Philippines for adventure and challenge purposes (32%), showing the strong interest of travelers in outdoor activities. Adventures with nature are the key reasons for traveling to a country and for seeking travel experiences. This shows that solo travel is becoming trendier and more popular. In terms of the preferred booking method of the travellers, half of the respondents (50%) preferred the use of booking applications. This shows a strong reliance on the power of technology, as it can provide real-time service transactions.

The following are the conclusions for part 2 which highlights the top push motivation in terms of Escape from Routine, Adventure and Challenge, Self-development and Learning, and Novelty and Exploration

The statement "The desire to avoid burnout from my routine pushes me to plan trips" got the highest average score, showing that escaping stress and routine is the strongest reason why tourist plan their travel. This also makes the top motivation from escape from routine indicators.

The statements "Overcoming fears during travel motivates me to explore new places" and "travelling allows me to test my mental resilience in unfamiliar situations" both got the highest mean score. These indicate that travelers are motivated by the challenges, which help them discover themselves and grow personally. Those two (2) aforementioned statements are the top motivations for adventure and challenge.

The statement "Learning about different cultures motivates me to plan trips" got the highest average score. This shows that cultural exposure is considered an important reason for travel, as travelers seek to broaden their understanding and enhance their global awareness. This statement is the top push motivation in terms of self-development and learning.

The statement "Exploring unfamiliar places is a primary reason I choose to travel" and "Traveling allows me to satisfy my curiosity about the world" both got the highest average score, showing that the desire for new experiences is a strong motivation for travel. These two (2) statements are the top push motivation in terms of novelty and exploration indicators.

The following statements represent the conclusion part 3, indicating the top pull motivations of the foreign respondents in terms of Infrastructure and Services, Cost and Affordability, Attraction and Activities, and Safety and Security.

The statement "Local staff (e.g., hotel, restaurant) were friendly and professional" got the highest mean score; this means that warm hospitality and professionalism really influence tourist satisfaction. Hence, positive tourist and staff interaction can enhance the overall travel experience, leaving the foreign travelers in awe and satisfied with the service they received. Therefore, this statement is the top pull motivations of the foreign tourist in terms of tourism infrastructure and services.

The statement "Discounts, promotions, or seasonal deals played a role in my decision to travel" got the highest mean score, demonstrating that the travelers are influenced by the different promotional offers, as well as discounted plane tickets, accommodation, and activity packages to a specific destination. This statement is revealed as the top pull motivation of foreign tourists in terms of cost and affordability.

The statement "Opportunities to explore natural landmarks (e.g., parks, wildlife)" got the highest mean score, showing that tourists are motivated by adventurous nature-based activities and outdoor experiences. The natural environment is a significant influence on why people choose to travel. This statement is therefore identified as the top pull motivations of the foreign tourist in terms of attraction and activities.

The statement "The availability of reliable emergency services", "Safe infrastructure is critical to my travel preference," and "A local community's friendliness and tolerance toward tourists affect my decision to visit" all got the highest mean scores. This finding shows that foreign travelers really value their safety in a tourist destination, there should be emergency services when needed, and welcoming local communities added a sense of belongingness and security to them. Therefore, the three (3) aforementioned statements are considered as the top motivational factors in terms of safety and security.

4.2 Significant relationship between the profile of the foreign tourist and their level of push motivations.

Findings conclude that the respondents' profile has a significant influence on their travel push motivations. It revealed that the civil status, income, and nationality are positively correlated with motivations related to escape from routine, adventure and challenge, and novelty and exploration. On the other hand, the purpose of visit, travel companion, and preferred booking method are negatively correlated with these motivations. Moreover, the null hypothesis is rejected, which confirms that the profile of the respondents and situational statement variables are essential in shaping the travelers' motivation and travel behavior.

4.3 Significant relationship between the profile of the foreign tourist and their level of pull motivations

The findings revealed that educational attainment, employment status, purpose of visit, travel companion, and preferred booking method are significantly correlated with the pull motivations of the respondents towards the tourism destination. On the other hand, the estimated monthly income did not exhibit a significant relationship; its positive direction only means a possible influence on satisfaction levels. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no relationship between the profile of the foreign tourists and their level of pull motivation is rejected, which confirms that the demographic profile has significant effects on the tourists' motivation and perceptions.

4.4 DIY travel plan strategy for foreign tourist

The proposed travel plan strategy focuses on flexibility, authenticity, customization, and a personalized travel experience. Findings revealed that the tourists' need for escape, self-discovery and learning, adventure and challenge, as well as novelty and exploration. Results show that the demographic profile of the respondents and the situational statement of perceived factors strongly affect both push and pull motivations. The main parts of the travel plan strategy are more focused on the safety and security, cost and affordability, infrastructure and services, as well as having a meaningful experience. Together, these findings can help make travel in the Philippines more sustainable and convenient for travelers, especially foreign tourists.

Compliance with ethical standards

Statement of ethical approval

The researcher ensured that all necessary guidelines and ethical standards were strictly followed prior to the conduct of the study, particularly during the data-gathering process that involved different respondents. Before the administration of the research instrument, the respondents were provided with an informed consent at the upper portion of the survey form that stated the purpose of the study, emphasizing that all collected data were used exclusively for academic purposes. The confidentiality and anonymity of the participants were maintained throughout the study to uphold ethical research practices and ensure the integrity of the data.

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